

Research article

Geolinguistic analysis of the spelling in the 1923 Burgundian text *L'âme du Morvan*

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Abstract: The first edition of the text, *L'âme du Morvan*, in the Morvan dialect was published in 1923. Morvan is in central Burgundy. Historically, it belonged to neighboring regions and was never united (Richard 1973: 153, 291). According to Ito (2020, 2021, 2022), no unified language was spoken in Morvan during the mid-20th century. In the 39 stories in this book, we find variations in spelling. Because some words are spelled differently in different stories, we hypothesize that the 39 stories could have been written in different spoken language and seek to determine which regional spoken language the stories were written in. First, we presume the pronunciations of forms representing 261 words across 39 stories. Second, we compare them with the pronunciations of 18 Morvan locations in the *Atlas Linguistique et Ethnographique de la Bourgogne* (ALB), the Linguistic Atlas of Burgundy. Based on the coincidence ratio of the 18 locations, we classify the 39 stories using cluster analysis. Next, we visualize the group that is the most consistent with the locations. Finally, we consider whether the 39 stories were written in the same spoken language or several spoken languages. The spelling analysis suggests that the 39 stories may have been written slightly differently; however, they were written in the dialect of the Saulieu region—the Bas-Morvan dialect.*

Keywords: *L'âme du Morvan*; Morvan; Burgundy; dialectology; geolinguistics

1. Introduction

Morvan is a region in the center of Burgundy, France, covering an area of 60 km from east to west and 100 km from north to south. It is a naturally beautiful area, enriched with forests and pools. Its central high-altitude area reaches approximately 900 m above sea level. The region was designated as *le Parc Naturel Régional du Morvan* (the Morvan Regional Natural Park) in 1973. The spoken language of Morvan is written as *morvandeau*, *morvandiau*, or *morvanelle*.¹ The dialect ceased

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¹ Le Trésor de la langue française informatisé (TLFi) <http://stella.atilf.fr/>

to be spoken in most parts of Burgundy by the 1960s, although there were still residents in Bresse and Morvan who spoke both the dialect and French (Taverdet 1973: 320–325) (see Figure 2).

Fig. 1 France

Fig. 2 Burgundy

2. Previous research on the Morvan dialect

2.1. Régnier (1979a, b), Bertrant (1979)

The three books by Régnier (1979a, b) and Bertrant (1979) constitute a series called *Les Parlers du Morvan*. Régnier (1979b) is a linguistic map of his survey in northern and central Morvan in the 1940s–1960s. He analyzed Morvan's spoken language phonetically, morphologically, and lexically (Régnier 1979a). Bertrant (1979) transcribed pronunciations found in the four provinces straddled by Morvan (Côte-d'Or, Saône-et-Loire, Yonne, and Nièvre) into spellings (see Figure 2 for provinces). Régnier (1979a: 186) posits that the spoken language of Morvan was the last barrier to the Burgundian dialect against the pressure of the Nivernais dialect from the West.

2.2. Ito (2020, 2021)

Ito (2020, 2021) geolinguistically analyzed the pronunciations of words with the same etymon, such as C(A)-, -CC(A), PL-, and BL-. The results confirm that in Morvan in the mid-20th century, words with the same etymon were capable of being pronounced differently, even at the same location, and no phonetically unified dialect was spoken. C(A)- and -CC(A) are widely distributed as [ʃ], while [s] forms a language island around the plateau of Morvan—or is continuous with [s] or [ts] in

southeastern Burgundy. This supports Dauzat’s theory that [ts] was once widespread throughout Burgundy (Dauzat 1944: 224–231) and Régnier’s theory that Morvan’s spoken language has something in common with Francoprovençal² (Régnier 1979a: 133–134). We also found that the boundaries—between [pl]/[bl], continuous from western Burgundy, and [pj]/[bj] continuous from eastern Burgundy—are complex in Morvan.

2.3. Ito (2022)

Ito (2022) analyzed linguistic-geographical subject personal pronouns and the verb « être » (present indicative) in Morvan in the 1960s. The results confirm the lack of phonetic unity with respect to subject personal pronouns and the forms of conjugation of this verb. In addition, the phonetic variations in the Burgundian dialect remained at relatively high elevations in central Morvan.

3. Dialect text *L’âme du Morvan*

L’âme du Morvan, in the 1923 edition, was published by Mrs. Gervais, who was an editor. It consists of 39 short stories, two theatrical scenarios, and descriptions of beliefs and customs. The author’s name is not printed, but “author A. Guillaume” is handwritten on the facing page of the digitized book available on Gallica.³

The book was reprinted in 1971 with Guillaume’s name as the author by the organization *les Amis du Vieux Saulieu* (the Friends of Old Saulieu). In addition to the contents of the 1923 edition, one scenario has been added. According to the preface of the 1971 edition, Alfred Guillaume was born in Saulieu (Figure 2). He worked as a veterinarian and was elected as the city’s first magistrate. The reprint was authorized by Miss Guillaume, Guillaume’s daughter, and Mrs. Guerrier, a descendant of Mrs. Gervais. The preface reads: “*L’âme du Morvan* was first published in 1923 ... Only a few copies bear the author’s name: Mr. A. Guillaume.” Based on this description, the 1923 edition is noted as Guillaume (1923). A part of the preface of the 1923 edition reads as follows:

We have brought together the stories that have already appeared in the published almanacs and those that have not yet been published. Finally, we have added the beliefs, customs, superstitions, proverbs, and sayings peculiar to the region ... All of these are written in the dialect of the Saulieu

² Francoprovençal is a language originally spoken in east-central France. Southeastern Burgundy belongs to this region.

³ Gallica is the Digital Library of *la Bibliothèque Nationale de France* (BnF) and its partners. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k98015409?rk=21459;2>

region, but with some differences; this is the dialect of the entire Bas-Morvan.⁴

3.1. Taverdet (2001)

According to Taverdet (2001: 210–211), Guillaume was a veterinarian and mayor of Saulieu, the capital of the Côte-d'Or canton. Taverdet states that traditional dialect authors did not write for the edification of patois speakers but for readers who were generally educated, wanted not to mock but to appreciate the peasantry, and liked to find old words (2001: 215).

3.2. Variations in spelling in the 39 stories of the 1923 edition

Among the 39 stories, we found variations in spelling, which can be classified into the following types.⁵

- Vowels

« place » (place): *place, plaice*

« roi » (king): *roi, roué*

- Consonants

« chambre » (room): *chambre, chambe*

« entendre » (hear): *entendre, entend'e*

- *l* or *i* after *p/b*

« blé » (wheat): *blé, bié*

- With or without a hyphen

« année » (year): *année, an-née*

- Compound variation (missing or replacing letters, inserting apostrophes).

« horloge » (clock): *heurloge, r'loge*

« regarder » (watch): *eurgairder, regairder, r'gairder*

- Synonyms

« brebis » (ewe): *borbis, oueille*

In terms of the relationship between stories and their variations, words can be grouped into three categories:

- 1) Words spelled uniformly in the 39 stories.
- 2) Words not spelled uniformly in the same story.
- 3) Words spelled differently in different stories.

We note that some words were spelled differently in different stories. As already mentioned, the preface to the 1923 edition states that the 39 stories are not the creation of a single author but a collection of existing stories and unpublished works.

⁴ Bas-Morvan is a plateau in the northern part of Morvan, connected to the Paris basin to the northwest.

⁵ Forms written in the corpus are italicized. « » denotes a word in standard French.

It also states that the entire book is “written in the dialect of the Saulieu region,” with “slight differences” ... nevertheless, “in the spoken language of Bas-Morvan.” Therefore, by analyzing the spellings, we can prove that the 39 stories were written in more than one spoken language.

4. Research question

The research question for this study is:

Which regional spoken language of Morvan were the 39 stories in *L'âme du Morvan* (1923 edition) written in?

The study is original because no research to date has analyzed the spellings of these stories in Guillaume (1923) from a geolinguistic perspective.

5. Methodology

5.1. Corpus

The 39 stories from the 1923 edition were used as the corpus in this study. They comprise utterances (in dialect or in SF⁶) and narration (in dialect). The utterances of certain persons, for example *monsieu* « monsieur, » are always written in SF. Phrases written in SF were excluded from the corpus. The size of the corpus is as follows:

- Word types: 8,308
- Word tokens: 56,673

As apostrophes sometimes appear inside a word, they were counted as letters. In other words, *tab'e* « table » (table) was recognized as a single word.

5.2. Analyzed words

Headwords of the *Atlas Linguistique et Ethnographique de la Bourgogne* (ALB), the Linguistic Atlas of Burgundy (261 words)⁷, were analyzed. They were selected based on the following criteria.

- 1) The meaning of form, representing 261 words, can be found in Morvan's *Dictionary of Dialects* (Chambure 1878) and the *Dictionary of Burgundian French* (Taverdet and Navette-Taverdet 1990). However, in the first note to

⁶ SF means standard French.

⁷ The 261 words include subject-verb conjugation combinations. For the sake of convenience, we use “word” in this study.

the first story, *Ein tor de couéchon*, the author writes: “To make patois easier to read and understand, we have adopted spellings that are as close as possible to French and to the pronunciations of words. We do not, therefore, follow the spelling indicated by Chambure in his Glossary” (Guillaume 1923: 7). When referring to Chambure (1878), it was necessary to investigate possible spellings rather than retain his spelling.

- 2) Substantive (nouns, adjectives, adverbs, infinitives of verbs, and conjugated forms of subjects and verbs).
- 3) Etymology of the FEW⁸.

Figure 3 shows that the forms representing the 261 words appeared 3,874 times in the corpus.

Fig. 3 The number of occurrences of forms representing the 261 words

Figure 4 shows the tokens and the number of analyzed words in each story. As expected, the greater the number of tokens, the greater the number of words analyzed.

Of the 261 words, 187 appeared in unified form in 39 stories. In contrast, 74 words had multiple forms: 32 were spelled differently in different stories, and 42 had multiple spellings in the same story.

⁸ von Wartburg (1922-2002) *Französisches etymologisches Wörterbuch. Eine Darstellung des galloromanischen Sprachschatzes*. (French Etymological Dictionary. A presentation of the Gallo-Roman vocabulary).

Fig. 4 The tokens and the number of the analyzed words in each story

5.3. 18 locations of Morvan in the *Atlas Linguistique et Ethnographique de la Bourgogne* (ALB)

Figure 5 shows The 18 locations of Morvan in the ALB: L27, L30, L52, L54, L62, L65, L70, L75, L77, L79, L80, L83, L85, L86, L89, L92, L93, and L102. The locations indicated by the dots were not used in this study.

Fig. 5 The 18 locations of Morvan in the ALB

5.4. Procedure

The relationship between spelling and pronunciation in the corpus was estimated by referring to the relationship between spelling and pronunciation in SF, based on Guillaume's approach (1923: 7): "To make patois easier to read and understand, we have adopted spellings that are as close as possible to French and to the pronunciations of words." The pronunciations were inferred from the forms representing the 261 words. Then, they were compared with the pronunciations of the 18 locations in the ALB for each story (classified "1" if they matched, and "0" if they

did not). The 39 stories were analyzed and classified into several clusters. The locations at which each cluster is most consistent was then determined.

6. Analysis

6.1. Pronunciation inference

The following validations of the relationship between spellings and pronunciations in the corpus were conducted to infer possible pronunciations from the forms representing the 261 words. Since the spoken Morvan language that this corpus was written in had not yet been determined, the pronunciations of all locations of Morvan in the ALB were used. Hence, the range of possible pronunciations was expanded.

Since Guillaume was a speaker of both dialect and SF, we assumed that the same spelling forms in SF were pronounced the same way as in SF.

6.1.1. Validation of the relation between vowel letters and pronunciations

When we refer to Catach's (1980: 62–75, 82–142) relationship between vowel graphemes and pronunciations in SF, some spellings are slightly inconsistent with pronunciations in the ALB. Generally, « é » is used for [e] and « è » for [ɛ] in SF. In the corpus, however, *é* is not always used to represent [e] and *è* is not always used to represent [ɛ]. The added graphemes and pronunciations are shown in bold (Table 1).

Table 1 Vowels graphemes and pronunciations in the corpus

Grapheme	Pronunciation	Grapheme	Pronunciation
a, â, â	[a], [ɑ]	an, am, em	[ã], [ã]
é, è, ê, ai, aî, ei, eai	[e], [ɛ]	en	[ã], [ẽ]
e	[e], [ɛ], [a*], [ə], ∅	in, ain	[ẽ], [ẽ]
i	[i]	oin, ouin	[wẽ], [wẽ]
o, ô, au	[o], [ɔ]	on, ôn	[õ]
ou, oû	[u]	oi	[wa], [wa]
u, û	[y]	oé	[we], [wɛ]
ü	[y], [y]	ou+vowel	[w]
u (+i)	[y], [y]	i, y, yi, il, ill	[j]
eu, œu, eû	[ø], [œ]		

The letter « â » could represent an open back vowel in SF. The pronunciation of *pâteure* seems to be [patø:r], indicated by the legend ○ in ALB 339: pâturage (pasture) (see figure 6). In the following, symbols represent legends in figures. In this

case, *â* represents an open back-vowel [ɑ]. In contrast, *crâcher* could be pronounced as ○[kraʃe] in ALB1328: cracher (to spit), with *â* indicating an open front vowel [a] (see Figure 7). These two maps show that *â* could be either an open front vowel [a] or an open back vowel [ɑ] in the corpus.

In SF, the vowel letters with circumflex such as « â, ê, î, ô, û » have some functions: to represent long vowels, to distinguish homophones, and to indicate traces of lost letters. Here, they were examined to determine whether they always represent long vowels in the corpus. The letter *î* was not used alone in the corpus.

⊗[paty:r], ○[patø:r], ●[pa:tʃi]
□[pa:ke], ■[pa:kjɛ], △[pa:ki],
▲[paki], ▲[pa:k]

Fig. 6 ALB339: pâturage

○[kraʃe], ●[krwɛʃe], ⊗[krɔʃe],
▲[krese], ☆[kœpe], ★[kœpre]

Fig. 7 ALB1328: cracher

As already mentioned, *pâteure* could be ○ [patø:r] in ALB339: pâturage and *crâcher* seems to be ○[kraʃe] in ALB1328: cracher (see Figures 6 and 7). In ALB111: saison, *sâyon* « saison » (season) seems to be ▲[sa:jõ] (see Figure 8). In the corpus, *â* could represent [ɑ], [ɑ:], and [a].

The forms *nouêr* and *nouair* for « noir » (black) seem to correspond to □[nwɛ:r] or to ■[nwɛr] in ALB1032: noir (see Figure 9). It is not possible to determine whether *ê* represents [ɛ:] or [ɛ].

○[sɛ:zõ], ●[sa:zõ], ▲[sa:jõ]

Fig. 8 ALB111: saison

Côyier for « collier » (necklace) could correspond to ⊙[ko:je] or to ○[koje] in ALB1254: collier (see Figure 10). The letter *ô* seems to represent [o:] or [o].

The form *tûyon* for « tison » (firebrand) could correspond to ○[ty:jð] in ALB1450: tison (see Figure 11). However, *trûyot* and *truyot* for « trèfle » (clover) could correspond to △[tryjo] in ALB330: trèfle (see Figure 12). It means that *û* could be [y:] ou [y].

Thus, the vowel letters with circumflex, *â*, *ê*, *ô*, *û*, could be long or short vowels, depending on forms.

□[nwɛ:r], ■[nwer], ☒[nwe:],
▣[nwɛ], ○[nwar], ●[nar], ⊙[nwa]

Fig. 9 ALB1032: noir

○[koje], ⊙[ko:je], ●[kuje]

Fig. 10 ALB1254: collier

○[ty:jð], ●[ty:zð], ⊙[ty:zð]
□[tø:jð], ■[tø:zð], ×[brezjo]

Fig. 11 ALB1450: tison

○[trɛf], △[tryjo], □[tru:jo], ☒[trɔlo]
☆[trylo], ★[try:lo], ×[tru:lo]

Fig. 12 ALB330: trèfle

The vowel letters without the circumflex cannot specifically represent short or long vowels in SF. We assumed that they were both represented in the corpus.

6.1.2. Validation of the relation between consonantal letters and pronunciations

Table 2 shows the relationship between consonant graphemes and pronunciations in the corpus. The grapheme « r » is pronounced as a uvular fricative [ʁ] in SF, but the ALB shows that it is an alveolar trill [r] in Morvan. For others, we referred to the relationship between graphemes and pronunciations in SF, following Catach (1980: 143–194).

Table 2 Consonant graphemes and pronunciations in the corpus

Grapheme	Pronunciation	Grapheme	Pronunciation
p	[p]	x, cc, xc	[ks], [gz]
b	[b]	ch	[ʃ]
t	[t]	j, g	[ʒ]
d	[d]	l	[l]
c, qu, k	[k]	r	[r]
g, gu	[g]	m	[m]
f, ph	[f]	n	[n]
v	[v]	gn	[ɲ]
s, ss, c, ç	[s]	ng	[ŋ]
vowel+s+vowel, z	[z]		

In SF, word-final consonants are generally voiceless. Conversely, « -l » and « -r » are, in general, voiced at the end of a word. However, « -r » is voiceless in infinitives with the ending « -er » and in some nouns with « -er ». In dialectal texts, because spellings are normally written to represent sounds, it is common to consider a consonant letter at the end of a word as voiced, if it exists. In the following section, we examine whether word-final consonant letters in the corpus could be pronounced. Of the 261 words, *sel* (salt) is spelled in the same manner as SF. However, there is no form with *-l* that differs from that of SF. Thus, *-l* is not verified.

The word « droit » (straight) has a « -t » that is voiceless in SF. In the corpus, it was spelled *drouet*. In ALB1301: droit, [t] was not pronounced in Morvan. The « -s » that indicates plurality is not pronounced in SF. In the corpus, the plural word « plumes » (feathers) is spelled *pleumes*. In ALB1187: les plumes, the [s] are not in Morvan. The unpronounced *-t* and *-s* are written in the corpus as well as in the SF. This clearly indicates the influence of SF on the spelling in the corpus.

The letter « -r » of « -er » in infinitives and some nouns is not pronounced in SF. The letter « -r » of « pêcher » (to fish) is not pronounced in SF. It is spelled *pouâcher* in the corpus, however, [r] does not appear in Morvan in ALB942: pêcher. The letter « -r » of « plancher » (floor) is also not pronounced in SF. It is spelled *plincher* and [r] is not pronounced in ALB1397: plancher. In Morvan, as in SF, -r can be voiceless in infinitives and nouns with -er. This clearly indicates the influence of SF.

Perhaps the author wrote the unpronounced word-final consonant letters as they are in SF so that readers would immediately know what the word was. Because the pronunciation of word-final consonants is strongly influenced by SF, the treatment of -r is generally considered to be the same as in SF.

6.2. Geolinguistic analysis

6.2.1. Coincident ratio

We compared the pronunciations inferred from the spellings with the pronunciations at the 18 locations. Our analysis of Story 6 is presented in Table 3. The leftmost column contains the 261 words. Of the 261 words, 24 appear in Story 6. The second column on the left represents the form of the story. A hyphen indicates that a word does not appear. The third column lists all pronunciations that can be inferred from these forms. All vowels are indicated as short; however, they may also be long. The right side of the table shows the pronunciations of the 18 ALB locations. « Vider » (to empty) is written as *queurer* in the corpus. From the spelling, pronunciations [køre], [køre], [køre], or [køre] can be inferred. At L27, « vider » is pronounced [køre]. Since it matches one of the guessed pronunciations, it counts as “1”. Because the inferred pronunciations do not match L30, L93, or L102, these locations are counted as “0.” Next, the coincident ratio for Story 6 was determined.

Table 4 shows the coincident ratio for all stories.

Table 3 The coincident ratio of Story 6

24/ 261 words	Corpus		ALB					
	Forms	Inferred pronunciations	Maps no.	L27	L30	...	L93	L102
« aider »	-	-	ALB1785	[ɛ:dje] 0	[ɛ:dje] 0		[ede] 0	[e:de] 0
...
« vider »	<i>queurer</i>	[køre][køre] [køre][køre]	ALB730	[køre] 1	[vide] 0		[vide] 0	[vide] 0
« cercueil »	<i>cerqueu</i>	[særkøj][særkøj] [særkøj][særkøj]	ALB1701	[særkøj] 0	[særkøj] 0		[særkøj] 0	[bjær] 0
Match score				18	19		9	9
Coincident ratio (= match score / 24 words)				0.75	0.79		0.38	0.38

Table 4 The coincident ratio of the 39 stories

Coincident ratio	ALB				
	27	30	...	93	102
Story 1	0.60	0.66		0.21	0.21
Story 2	0.55	0.63		0.39	0.42
...
Story 38	0.68	0.74		0.35	0.32
Story 39	0.60	0.60		0.32	0.31

6.2.2. Cluster analysis

Ward's square Euclidean distance method and the coincident ratio of the 18 locations⁹ were used for the cluster analysis (see Table 4). Based on the resulting dendrogram, the 39 stories were classified into four clusters (see Figure 13). Cluster 1 consists of Story 34 only; Cluster 2 consists of stories 1, 10, 12, 14, 15, 18, 20, 21, 22, 24, 25, 27, 28, 30, 31, 33, 35, 36, 37, and 39; Cluster 3 consists of 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 17, 23, and 26; and Cluster 4 consists of 4, 8, 9, 11, 13, 16, 19, 29, 32, and 38.

⁹ We used R that is a language and environment for statistical computing and graphics similar to S. <http://cran.r-project.org/>

Fig. 13 Dendrogram

The average matching rate was then calculated (Table 7). This was determined by dividing the total matching scores by the sample size (see Tables 5 and 6). The total match score was the sum of the match scores for the stories in each cluster.

Table 5 The total match score

Locations	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
L27	10	576	160	211
L30	10	657	187	231
L52	6	490	132	170
L54	10	463	121	172
L62	5	347	115	130
L65	11	486	147	186
L70	3	313	111	101
L75	5	393	134	134
L77	3	277	94	87
L79	5	383	122	148
L80	6	483	150	170
L83	5	393	136	136
L85	1	396	128	131
L86	2	339	115	104
L89	2	390	127	137
L92	2	331	106	96
L93	2	302	104	90
L102	3	297	102	88

The sample size was the total number of words analyzed in the stories.

Table 6 The sample size

	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Sample size	15	974	262	297

Table 7 The average matching rate

Locations	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
L27	67%	59%	61%	71%
L30	67%	67%	71%	77%
L52	40%	50%	50%	57%
L54	67%	48%	46%	58%
L62	33%	36%	44%	43%
L65	73%	50%	56%	62%
L70	20%	32%	42%	34%
L75	33%	40%	51%	45%
L77	20%	28%	36%	29%
L79	33%	39%	47%	49%
L80	40%	50%	57%	57%
L83	33%	40%	52%	45%
L85	7%	41%	49%	44%
L86	13%	35%	44%	35%
L89	13%	40%	48%	46%
L92	13%	34%	40%	32%
L93	13%	31%	40%	30%
L102	20%	30%	39%	29%

6.2.3. Mapping

The average matching rate was placed on a map using the cartographic tool—Shiny Dialect.¹⁰ The numbers in the figure represent the 18 locations.

¹⁰ It was developed in the framework of ECLATS (*Extraction de contenus géolinguistiques d'atlas et analyse spatiale*), a project supported by ANR (*Agence Nationale de la Recherche*).
http://lig-tdcge.imag.fr/shiny/ShinyDialectV1_2_10/

Fig. 14 Mapped average matching rate

Figure 14 shows that Cluster 1 has an average matching rate of at least 70% with L65 and at least 60% with L27, L30, and L54. Cluster 2 has at least 60% with L30. In Cluster 3, L30 and L27 had a match of over 70%, and over 60%, respectively. In Cluster 4, L27 and L30 match by more than 70%, and L65 by more than 60%. None of the clusters have a high average matching rate with the southwestern Morvan.

6.3. Discussion

Clusters 2, 3, and 4 are most consistent with L30. In contrast, Cluster 1 was the most consistent with L65, followed by L27, L30, and L54. Story 34, the only story comprising Cluster 1, has the lowest number of tokens and words analyzed (see Figure 4). While this may have influenced the analysis, Stories 13 and 16—which have similarly low numbers of tokens and analyzed words—are classified in Cluster 4. After all, Story 34 could be unique.

Regardless, the four clusters are close to the spoken language at around L30, L27, and L65. Figure 15 shows that L30 is the closest to Saulieu, with a linear distance of approximately 4 km. L27 and L65 are approximately 9 and 11 km from Saulieu, respectively.

Fig. 15 Saulieu and nearby locations

7. Conclusion

In answer to the research question, “Which regional spoken language of Morvan were the 39 stories in *L’âme du Morvan* (1923 edition) written in?” we can say that they were written in the spoken language of the Saulieu region. Spelling analysis suggests that the 39 stories may have been written slightly differently; however, they were written in the dialect of the Saulieu region—the Bas-Morvan dialect. This confirms the statement in the preface to the 1923 edition.

By incorporating the relationship between the spelling and pronunciation of standard French, the author wrote forms that readers could easily associate with the words in standard French. He also introduced his own spelling to represent pronunciation. On the other hand, he did not insist on faithfully reproducing the pronunciation of word-final consonants but wrote down the unpronounced word-final consonant according to standard French spelling.

A partial summary of the preface to the 1923 edition states:

Regions of France are losing their originality and individuality. This is inevitable, even in Morvan, which has long remained faithful to its traditions without accepting anything new. We have dreamed of making a small contribution to saving the language of our ancestors from total

extinction or oblivion, in the hope of preserving the memory of this dying life.

This study has shown that the spoken language of the author's hometown has been preserved, mainly from a phonetic point of view, and that his goal has been achieved with the publication of this book.

In the future, we will analyze whether each story's spelling is unique. We will pay attention to Story 34, as we found unique phonetic features in this study, and explore whether Story 34's spelling is also distinctive.

Abbreviations

ALB	<i>Atlas linguistique et ethnographique de la Bourgogne</i>
FEW	von Wartburg, Walther (1922-2002) <i>Französisches etymologisches Wörterbuch. Eine Darstellung des galloromanischen Sprachschatzes</i>
SF	standard French

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